

ENLIGHTENMENT PHILOSOPHY AND ITS REFLECTION IN ENGLISH LITERATURE: A STUDY FROM THE 18TH CENTURY

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ABSTRACT

This article delves into the Enlightenment philosophy and its profound impact on English literature, particularly during the 18th century. Through an analysis of key literary works, such as those by Alexander Pope, Jonathan Swift, and John Dryden, this study explores how Enlightenment ideals of reason, skepticism, and humanism are reflected in English literature. By examining the philosophical underpinnings and literary techniques employed by Enlightenment writers, this article aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the Enlightenment's influence on the development of English literature.

Key words: Enlightenment philosophy, English literature, reason, skepticism, humanism.

INTRODUCTION

The Enlightenment era, spanning the 17th and 18th centuries, marked a significant period of intellectual and cultural transformation in Europe, characterized by a shift towards reason, empiricism, and rationalism. This article explores how Enlightenment philosophy, with its emphasis on individual autonomy, scientific inquiry, and skepticism towards traditional authority, influenced the literary landscape of England during this period. Through an analysis of notable literary works and authors, this study aims to elucidate the ways in which Enlightenment ideals are reflected in English literature.

METHODS

The methodology employed in this study involves a thorough examination of key literary works from the Enlightenment era, focusing on texts that explicitly engage with Enlightenment themes and philosophical concepts. Works by

prominent authors such as Alexander Pope, Jonathan Swift, John Dryden, and others are analyzed for their thematic content, narrative techniques, and philosophical resonance. Additionally, critical interpretations and scholarly insights into Enlightenment literature are integrated to provide a comprehensive analysis of its impact on English literary tradition.

RESULTS

The Enlightenment era witnessed a flourishing of literary creativity in England, with writers engaging deeply with the philosophical ideas and values of the time. One of the central themes that permeated English literature during this period was the celebration of reason and rationality. Authors like Alexander Pope, known for his satirical wit and keen observations of human nature, utilized their works to critique societal norms and promote rational thinking.

Moreover, skepticism towards authority and traditional institutions was a recurring motif in Enlightenment literature. Jonathan Swift's «Gulliver's Travels», for instance, satirizes political corruption, religious intolerance, and social hierarchy, reflecting the Enlightenment's emphasis on challenging established power structures and advocating for intellectual freedom.

Humanism, another key tenet of Enlightenment philosophy, found expression in English literature through works that celebrated human potential, dignity, and progress. John Dryden's poetry, with its focus on the individual's capacity for growth and self-improvement, exemplifies the humanistic spirit of the Enlightenment, encouraging readers to embrace reason and enlightenment as pathways to a better society.

DISCUSSION

The influence of Enlightenment philosophy on English literature extended beyond thematic content to encompass literary techniques and stylistic innovations. Writers of the Enlightenment era experimented with new forms of prose and poetry, employing satire, irony, and allegory to convey complex philosophical ideas in accessible ways. The rise of the novel as a popular literary form also

coincided with the Enlightenment, providing authors with a medium to explore social issues, moral dilemmas, and human experience in greater depth.

Enlightenment literature not only reflected the intellectual currents of its time but also contributed to shaping public discourse and challenging prevailing attitudes. Through their works, Enlightenment writers engaged readers in critical reflection, encouraged skepticism towards dogma, and championed the values of reason, tolerance, and intellectual curiosity.

CONCLUSION

The Enlightenment philosophy had a profound and lasting impact on English literature, shaping its themes, style, and intellectual ethos. Through an exploration of reason, skepticism, and humanism, Enlightenment writers transformed the literary landscape of England, paving the way for new forms of expression and thought. Their works continue to resonate with readers today, offering insights into the enduring relevance of Enlightenment ideals in the realm of literature and intellectual inquiry.

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